

TASKS OF MUSIC AND MUSIC CULTURE CLASSES

Akhadjon Mamadaliyev

State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

Associate professor of the "Performance in folk instruments"
department, honorary professor of the Turan Academy of Sciences
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10815841>

Annotation: The realization of the goals and objectives of musical education directly depends on the lessons of musical culture in secondary schools. In the concept of musical education, musical science at school acquires to qualitatively new level along with other subjects. In order to raise musical education to qualitatively new level, it is considered an equal science in school.

Keywords: school, music, upbringing, culture, education, professional, goal, method.

Introduction.

The emergence of music goes back to ancient times. As a person is formed as a conscious, intelligent being, as mutual relations and problems are restored, he discovers soothing methods and sounds. Since our earliest ancestors were mainly engaged in hunting, the first samples of music were created in this style. It is possible to talk about this and give many examples of interrelated phenomena. Only the people of the peaceful country sing and dance. Otherwise, nothing will fit the heart. It is good that the number of singers and groups is increasing, but it is necessary to listen and sort them with a wide heart. People always live with dreams, there are many young people who live with the dream of singing a song. Therefore, it is known from our history that our wise people have not only loved music and song since ancient times, but also considered it as an important part of their cultural life. It is a dream of parents to teach their child to sing in the family. It has become a tradition for every household to have a musical instrument playing around the house. It was not in vain to say Allah to the child in the cradle, to call the adhan in the child's ear when the name was given, and to circumcise the boy under the sound of trumpets and trumpets.

A person who holds a song in his hand will never go to prison, - says our wise people. The great power of music has been evaluated in the oldest rare sources and in the teachings written by our encyclopedic scholars and wise scholars. Music, by its nature and emotional power, was considered an expression of the mind superior to wisdom and philosophy [1]

Music and spirituality are complementary. In today's society, we are trying to establish high spirituality in the hearts of young people. But without analyzing the situation of demand, supply, music promotion and advertising in the music market, it is difficult to achieve the desired result in this matter.

First of all, in terms of demand. When we talk about youth music, we need to know what kind of music young people are most in demand of. Performers often say that they perform such and such works because there is a demand for them. But we all know that there are very few works offered by professional musicians among them. After all, whatever we offer to the listener in the market of musical works, he will accordingly look for works for himself and buy some of them. At this point, the question directly goes back to the issue of promotion of

musical works. It is clear which direction and content of music is being promoted today. Private radio and TV channels have been leading the way in promoting some music works whose quality is disputed. It's true that nobody is strictly determining the repertoire they present on the air today. However, despite the fact that these institutions are private, we think that they are responsible for contributing to the work of establishing spirituality in our society.

Sometimes we talk about the fact that young people do not like listening to modern tunes - songs created in the style of classical music or folk music, performed to the accompaniment of national instruments. But we don't even think about why they don't listen to these works.

The listener is often conscious of listening to familiar music. Therefore, it is necessary to create an opportunity for young people to listen more to samples of music in the direction mentioned above. That is, radio and television should broadcast more such works.

In general, the promotion of musical works of a high artistic level is not in demand today. In addition, it is possible to know the number of concerts of instrumental works and repertoires of concert pieces. If enough attention is paid to this issue, we would prepare the ground for the growth of the artistic musical level of the listeners, especially the youth, for the development of musical culture, and for the growth of spirituality.

The sounds of music express the most noble, high and delicate human experiences, regardless of the people or the representative of the nation.

The realization of the goals and tasks of music education directly depends on the lessons of "Musical culture" in secondary schools. In the concept of music education, music at school, along with other subjects, has a special importance. In order to improve the quality of music education, it is considered a subject with equal rights in the school. This requires the modern student to have a positive attitude towards lessons, to properly organize and manage the development of students' musical activities. "Musical culture" as a lesson activity has its own characteristics [2].

Every teacher should know these features.

First of all, the music history theory includes some exercises of various examples of performance, music literacy training, music listening, music education and literature, children's musical instrument playing, elements of performing rhythmic movements, and the activities of creators in music.

Secondly, music differs from other forms of art in its means of expression, i.e. "language". If fiction is expressed with words, visual arts with color, and dance with artistic movements, then the melodic tool created from musical sounds is used.

Thirdly, music has an active emotional impact on students, evokes positive instructions and experiences. The program on the subject of "Music culture" in secondary schools should provide for the integration of stages of education such as listening to music, singing as a team, musical literacy, children's instruments and performing rhythmic movements of music creators in one lesson. In modern training, music perception plays an important role as a leading activity. Because at this stage, there are more game features in students' activities.

References:

1. www.ziyonet.uz taken from the site.

2.Odilov A.I., Kozimov J.J. Use of pedagogical technologies in music culture classes.
School education. Article.

